

Evaluation of Anti-urolithiatic Activity of *Bryophyllum sp.* in Inhibition of Calcium Oxalate Crystallization

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to elucidate the anti-urolithiatic activity (in vitro) of the aqueous leaf extract of *Bryophyllum pinnatum*, traditionally recognized for its therapeutic properties. The *B. pinnatum* leaves were collected and extracted using distilled water. Standard qualitative phytochemical tests were performed to detect the active bioactive compounds in the extract. The anti-urolithiatic activity (in vitro) of the aqueous extract was assessed through nucleation inhibition, aggregation and growth of the crystal suppression assays. Additionally, the percentage dissolution of urinary calculi was evaluated using an egg membrane model. The results of the present study confirmed a dose-dependent and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in vitro anti-urolithiatic activity exhibited by aqueous extract of *B. pinnatum* leaves. This study demonstrated the significant anti-urolithiatic potential of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract, attributed to its phytochemical components. These findings provide foundational evidence, necessitating further research on its efficacy in animal models and potential human applications.

Keywords: Dry powder inhalers, DPI device design, Patent challenging, DPI patent disputes, DPI Biologics

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are recognized as a valuable source of bioactive phytoconstituents, which have garnered significant attention due to their potential in drug discovery and therapeutic applications (Tekuri et al., 2019). These plants are particularly esteemed for their safety profile, with fewer adverse effects compared to synthetic drugs (Prasathkumar et al., 2021). While numerous plant species have been studied for their therapeutic potential, further investigation is needed to explore the full range of bioactive compounds in certain medicinal plants for drug discovery.

Urolithiasis, characterized by the development of stones in kidney is owed to extreme saturation of urine and infections due to bacteria in urinary tract, is a widespread disorder affecting approximately 12% of the global population. Urolithiasis is a multifactorial disease influenced by various biochemical, genetic and epidemiological factors, and it can lead to severe complications if left untreated. In India, kidney stones are highly prevalent, with about 12% of the population affected. This condition is particularly

concerning in North India, where up to 15% of the population suffers from kidney stones (Ganesamoni et al., 2012). The reappearance rate for the kidney stones is notably higher in men, with reports indicating a recurrence rate of 70-81% (male) and 47-60% (female) (Priyanka et al., 2018).

In India, eating habits and dietary aspects is recognized as a key role in kidney stones formation. High consumption of animal protein has been associated with increased urinary calcium excretion, reduced urine pH and lower citrate excretion are found to be the common reasons for kidney stone formation (Guha et al., 2019). Most commonly, the kidney stones (approximately 80%) consist of calcium depositions, primarily in the form of calcium oxalate (CaOx), while the remaining stones are made up of ammonium magnesium phosphate (struvite) (Evan, 2010). Calcium oxalate kidney stones are seemed to occur as monohydrate and dihydrate. The monohydrate stones being more stable and commonly associated with clinical cases (Khan et al., 2012). Struvite stones are formed due to infections in the

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

urinary tract triggered by specific bacteria, including *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Staphylococcus sp.* and *Proteus sp.*

Among the medicinal plants studied for their potential in managing urolithiasis, *Bryophyllum pinnatum* stands out for its long history of use in treating urinary stones in India and other parts of the world (Nagaratna et al., 2015). Known for its phytochemical diversity, *B. pinnatum* is a member of the family of Crassulaceae and commonly called as "air plant" or "miracle leaf." Despite its widespread use, scientific evidence supporting its anti-urolithiatic properties remains limited. The present study aims to evaluate the anti-urolithiatic activity of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract, exploring its potential as an effective and affordable therapeutic option for kidney stone prevention and management.

METHODS

Sample collection and Screening of Phytochemical constituents

The leaves of the plant (*B. pinnatum*) were collected from 45 days old plant in a nursery garden and was authenticated by the Department of Botany, Lady Doak College, Madurai. The leaves were washed, subjected to drying at room temperature. Dried leaves were extracted with sterile distilled water using Soxhlet extractor for 48h. After Soxhlet extraction, the filtrate was collected and stored at 4° C. The aqueous extract was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis by standard methods (Sofowora, 1993).

Fabrication of synthetic Calcium oxalate stones

The calcium oxalate kidney stones were prepared through homogenous method of precipitation (Jha et al., 2016). The mixture of calcium chloride dihydrate and sodium oxalate was kept in magnetic stirrer for precipitation. The resulting residues were washed thrice using distilled water. The calcium oxalate residues were dried at 60°C and used as synthetic calcium oxalate kidney stones for further analysis.

Determination of Anti-urolithiatic activity

Nucleation inhibition assay

The inhibitory activity of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract on the nucleation of CaOX kidney stones was determined by following the procedure described by Sharma et al. (2016). A buffer containing Tris-HCl (0.05M; pH 6.5), NaCl (0.15M), calcium chloride (5mM) and sodium oxalate was used for the assay. Calcium chloride was mixed with varying concentrations of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract (200 to 1000 µg/mL). Sodium oxalate was added to the above suspension to initiate crystallization. The above suspension was incubated at room temperature. The optical density was measured at 620 nm using a spectrophotometer and the percentage inhibition was calculated. Further, the influence of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract on the crystallization ability of calcium oxalate kidney stones was visualized using a light microscope.

Inhibition of the growth of calcium oxalate stones

The inhibition of the growth of calcium oxalate crystals was evaluated following the method of Bawari et al. (2018). CaCl₂ solution and Na₂C₂O₄ solution were added to solution containing Tris-HCl (10 mM) buffered with NaCl (90 mM). The calcium oxalate stones were added to above mixture and varying concentrations of aqueous extract of the leaves of *B. pinnatum* were also added and incubated at room temperature. The inhibition of the growth of the calcium oxalate crystals was measured at an absorbance of 620 nm.

Inhibition of Aggregation of calcium oxalate stones

The inhibition of the aggregation of calcium oxalate stones by the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was evaluated by following the procedure of Atmani et al. (2003). Calcium oxalate monohydrate crystals were fabricated and reconstituted in Tris buffer (pH 6.5) to a concentration of 0.8 mg/mL. Varying concentrations of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was incubated with calcium oxalate monohydrate crystals at room temperature. The inhibition of calcium oxalate stones aggregation was measured at an absorbance of 620 nm.

Preparation of Semi-permeable membrane from Eggs

The semi-permeable membrane of eggs lies in between the outer calcified shell and the inner

contents like albumin and yolk. The apex of eggs was punctured and the entire contents were squeezed out. Empty eggs were washed thoroughly in distilled water and placed in a beaker containing Conc. HCl (2M) for decalcification. The next day, the semipermeable membranes were carefully removed from the egg shell and washed with distilled water. The traces of acid present in the membrane were neutralised by placing the shell membranes in ammonia solution. After neutralisation, the semi-permeable membranes are rinsed with distilled water and stored at 4°C at a pH of 7-7.4 (Raj et al., 2024).

Estimation of Calcium Oxalate by titrimetric method

The dissolution percentage of calcium oxalate was evaluated by following the procedure of Jha et al. (2016). The samples were allowed to suspend in conical flasks containing Tris buffer (0.1 M) for 7 hrs at room temperature. After incubation, the contents in the semi-permeable membrane were transferred into test tubes containing sulphuric acid (1 N). The resulting mixture was titrated against KMnO₄ solution until light pink color was observed. Water was used

as the negative control and the commercial drug was used as positive control.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The anti-urolithiatic property of many herbal folk remedies make them indispensable for preventing disease. This article aims to highlight the use of *B. pinnatum* as a potent anti-urolithiatic herb. The leaves of *B. pinnatum* are reported to be a rich repository of varied phytochemicals with therapeutic potential. The results of the present study also adorn the above findings and illustrate the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins and terpenoids (Table 1). Absence of steroids and glycosides illustrates the advantages of using *B. pinnatum* leaves as a remedy for various ailments. Kumar et al. (2012) reported that phytochemicals such as kaempferol-3-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-rhamnogalactoside, tannins could be effective in dissolution of the calcium oxalate kidney stones. Saha and Verma (2013) reported that saponins have anti-crystallization property. Flavonoids are reported to have calcium oxalate dissolution property. Further, it has also been reported in a recent study that tannins and polyphenols inhibit and dissolve calcium oxalate crystal formation.

Table 1 Phytochemical constituents (Qualitative analysis) of *B. pinnatum* leaves

Phytochemicals	Test	Observation	Inference
Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	Purple ring at the interface.	+
Amino acids	Ninhydrin reagent	Violet color	+
Alkaloid	Mayer's test	Yellow color precipitate	+
Flavonoid	Alkaline reagent test	Deep yellow color	+
Phenol	Test with ferric chloride	Dark blue	+
Tannins	Test with ferric chloride	Dark blue	+
Saponins	Foam test	Foam	+
Steroids	Salkowski test	Absence of Red color	-
Terpenoids	Salkowski test	Reddish brown coloration of the inter face	+
Glycosides	Keller-Kiliani Test	Absence of Violet ring formation	-

Supersaturation of urine, nucleation and aggregation of crystal growth are various steps involved in urine stone formation. Hence, in the present study, the influence of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract on the various steps of calcium oxalate crystal formation was analysed.

Nucleation of calcium oxalate crystals was analysed and the results are tabulated and represented in table 2. The *B. pinnatum* leaf extract revealed a significant inhibition of calcium oxalate crystal nucleation in a dose-dependent manner. An inhibitory effect of 71% was observed at a concentration of 1000 µg/mL. Aqueous extract of *B. pinnatum* showed less

percentage inhibition compared to the standard drug. Additionally, the nucleation activity of *B. pinnatum* extract was also confirmed by detecting the changes of calcium oxalate crystals in microscope. Based on the microscopic analysis, it was evident that the number of calcium oxalate crystals was abridged in the presence of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract. It is obvious that the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract and the standard drug instigated the termination of calcium oxalate crystal

nucleation and were also less dense when compared to the control (Figure 1), revealing that the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract can avert the reaction of calcium chloride and sodium oxalate from creating calcium oxalate crystals, revealing the anti-lithiatic property. Saha and Verma (2013) stated a decrease in the calcium oxalate crystals designed in the incidence of rhizome extract.

Figure 1. Microscopic examination of calcium oxalate stones

(A) Untreated (B) Treated with *B. pinnatum* leaf extract (1000µg/mL) (C) Treated with standard drug (1000µg/mL)

Calcium oxalate crystal formation is a vital process in the kidney stone formation. In the initial stages, the crystal nucleus attains a critical size, grows to form a small, tough structure and results in the formation of kidney stone (Kulkarni et al., 2017). Therefore, in the present study, the calcium oxalate crystal development has been examined with the presence and absence of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract. The growth

inhibition of calcium oxalate crystal was assessed spectrophotometrically. The leaf extract of *B. pinnatum* had a dose dependent inhibitory activity on the growth of CaOx crystals (table 2). *B. pinnatum* leaf extract revealed an increased inhibition at 1000 µg/ml (69.81±1.15%) and the standard exhibited a maximum percent inhibition at 1000 µg/ml (87.30±1.52%).

Table 2 Nucleation and Growth Inhibition of Calcium oxalate stones

Sample	Concentration (µg/mL)	Nucleation Inhibition (%)	Inhibition of growth (%)
Aqueous extract (<i>B. pinnatum</i>)	200	32.30±1.21	39.00±2.00
	400	48.70±0.70	52.32±0.50
	600	59.50±1.01	55.30±1.15
	800	65.20±0.66	62.60±1.15
	1000	71.00±0.51	69.81±1.15
Standard drug	200	51.40±1.41	40.60±0.57
	400	62.50±0.97	49.00±1.00
	600	68.2±0.69	63.00±0.57
	800	72.10±0.46	74.60±2.30
	1000	83.90±0.40	87.30±1.52

In general, the calcium oxalate crystals associate together to form compound particles, which is known as crystal aggregation. It is the most significant and vital step in formation of kidney stones (Aggarwal et

al., 2013). In the present research, the crystal aggregation was evaluated by the change in absorbance in the presence of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract compared to a control. *B. pinnatum* leaf extract

showed maximum inhibition of 85.34% at 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. It was found that increasing the concentration of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract caused an increase in the

percentage inhibition of calcium oxalate aggregation. These results were compatible with the results reported by Saha and Verma (2013).

Figure 2 Inhibition of aggregation of calcium oxalate stones

The egg membrane assay reaction is depicted in figure 3. The dissolution percentage by the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract of at 800 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration was 59.24%. Dissolution percentage by the standard drug at 800 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration was 68.34% (Figure 4). The present study revealed that the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract has a dissolution ability comparable to that of the standard drug. This study has given primary evidence of *B. pinnatum* possessing anti-urolithiatic activity.

Figure 3 Decalcification of eggshell

Figure 4 Dissolution percentage of Calcium oxalate stones

CONCLUSION

The results of the study disclose that the leaf extract of *B. pinnatum* effectively inhibits the growth of calcium crystal and reduces the deposition of oxalate crystals. These findings suggest that *B. pinnatum* contains a range of bioactive compounds that contribute to its anti-urolithiatic activity. Associated to the standard medication, which contains multiple herbs with higher bioactive compound concentrations, *B. pinnatum*, a single herb, showed comparable anti-urolithiatic effects. This indicates that key bioactive compounds in *B. pinnatum* are responsible for its significant therapeutic efficacy. Furthermore, this study aligns with traditional South Indian knowledge and provides laboratory-based evidence supporting the plant's anti-urolithiatic potential. Future studies, including animal model experiments and in silico analyses, will provide further insights into the potential human applications of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract.

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HOW TO CITE: Kuzhandai Raj Selvaraj, Alagarsamy Malaisamy, Usha Chockaiyan*, Evaluation of Anti-urolithiatic Activity of *Bryophyllum* sp. in Inhibition of Calcium Oxalate Crystallization, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 454-459. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17864470>

